

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS AND PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN THE CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ SYSTEM

Aliyev I.,

Doctor of Chemistry, prof. hands. lab

Ismailova S.,

Research assistant

*Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry named after M.F. Nagiyev
of the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Ahmedova C.,

Ph.D., Associate Prof.

Adiyaman University, Faculty of Science and

Literature, Faculty of Chemistry, Turkey

Tagiyev S.

Ph.D., Associate Prof.

Azerbaijan Technical University

Abstract

Using physicochemical methods of analysis: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray analysis (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as by measuring density and microhardness, samples were studied in a wide range of concentrations of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system and its phase structure was constructed T-x diagram. It has been established that the phase diagram of CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ is partially quasi-binary, characterized by eutectic equilibrium and peritectic transformation. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on CuCr₂Te₄ reach up to 8 mol % CrAsTe₃, and solid solutions based on CrAsTe₃ are practically not determined.

Keywords: system, phase, eutectic, microhardness, solidus.

Introduction

The components of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system are synthesized from the compounds As₂Te₃, CuTe and Cr₂Te₃. Now let's get acquainted with the properties of all three components. The As₂Te₃ compound is a crystalline semiconductor. The As₂Te₃ compound and phases obtained on its basis are photosensitive materials [1-4]. A large number of systems involving the As₂Te₃ compound have been studied [5-11]. Ternary phases based on copper chalcogenides are widely used in the electronics industry as superionic materials [12-14]. Compounds with a spinel structure containing CuCr₂X₄ (X-S, Se, Te), obtained between Cr₂Te₃ and CuTe alloys, are materials with high ferromagnetic properties [15-17]. A number of complex systems with the presence of CuCr₂X₄ (X-S, Se, Te) compounds have been studied [18-21].

The purpose of this work is to synthesize composite alloys of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system and study their physicochemical properties and construct their phase diagram.

The CrAsTe₃ compound melts incongruently at 490°C and crystallizes in a tetragonal syngony with lattice parameters: $a = 14.246 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 5.993 \text{ \AA}$, $\rho_{\text{pucn.}} = 6.57 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho_{\text{X-ray}} = 6.96 \text{ g/cm}^3$ [22]. The CuCr₂Te₄ compound melts at 1155°C and crystallizes in the cubic syngony with a lattice constant $a = 11.143 \text{ \AA}$ [23]. The CuCr₂Te₄ compound has a phase transition at 810°C.

Experimental part

Before the synthesis of alloys of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system, the initial components CrAsTe₃ and CuCr₂Te₄ were synthesized. Then alloys of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system were synthesized by melting in a quartz ampoule with air suction to a pressure of

0.133 Pa in the temperature range 800-1200°C. After this, the alloys of the system were subjected to homogenizing annealing at a temperature of 300°C for 350 hours. Equilibrium samples were studied using physicochemical analysis methods.

Differential-thermal analysis was carried out on a low-frequency NTR-73 device. Al₂O₃ was taken as the standard. Chromel-alumel was used as a thermocouple. The heating rate was 9°C/deg.

X-ray phase analysis (XPA) was carried out on a D2 PHASER X-ray diffractometer. In this case, CuK α radiation and a Ni filter were used. Analysis of the microstructure of the samples was carried out using a MIM-8 microscope. In well-polished samples, a chromium solution was used as a mordant to separate the phases. The microhardness of the alloys was measured using a PMT-3 metallographic microscope. The density of the samples was determined by the pycnometric method; toluene was used as a working solution.

Results and its discussion

To clarify the nature of chemical processes in the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system, samples were synthesized in a wide concentration range. The alloys of the system are obtained in the form of a compact mass. Alloys rich in CrAsTe₃ compounds are bright silver in color, while alloys rich in CuCr₂Te₄ compounds are black in color. The operating time of each semiconductor material in a certain area depends on its resistance to the external environment. Therefore, the relationship between the alloys of the system and the influence of the external environment was studied. Although the system's alloys are resistant to air, water and organic solvents, they are highly soluble in strong acids (HNO₃, HCl).

Fig. 1. Microstructures of alloys of the $\text{CrAsTe}_3\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system.
a) 30, b) 92 mol % CrAsTe_3 .

The results of differential thermal analysis of alloys show that two and three endothermic effects were detected in their thermograms. As a result of studying the microstructure of the alloys, it was established that there are relatively large areas of solid solutions based on CuCr_2Te_4 . It was revealed that in a system based on the CuCr_2Te_4 compound, the solubility reaches 8 mol %, whereas in terms of the CrAsTe_3 compound the solubility range is practically not established. The remaining alloys in the solid state are two-phase.

To clarify the boundary of the solid solution region based on the CuCr_2Te_4 compound, alloys containing 3, 5, 8 and 10 mol % CrAsTe_3 . Then, after heat treatment of the samples at a temperature of 300°C for 240 hours, a microstructural analysis of these samples was carried out and it was found that at room temperature the solubility based on the CuCr_2Te_4 compound reaches up to 8 mol % CrAsTe_3 . In fig. 1 shows the microstructures of alloys in two-phase (a) and single-phase (b).

Fig. 2. Diffractograms of alloys of the $\text{CrAsTe}_3\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system.
1– CrAsTe_3 , 2-30, 3-70, 4-92, 5-100 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 .

To confirm the results of DTA and microstructural analysis, X-ray phase analysis of the alloys was carried out. X-ray images were obtained for alloys containing 30, 70 and 92 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 (Fig. 2).

A comparison was made of X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys containing 30, 70 and 92 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 , with X-ray diffraction lines of the original components. As a result, it was found that in the diffraction patterns of alloys containing 30, 70 mol %

CuCr_2Te_4 consist of a mixture of diffraction lines of the original components, that is, the alloys are two-phase. A diffraction pattern containing 92 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 are identical to the X-ray diffraction pattern of CuCr_2Te_4 . This means that this alloy is a solid solution based on CuCr_2Te_4 . In table Table 1 shows some physicochemical properties of alloys of the $\text{CrAsTe}_3\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system.

As can be seen from table. 1, the microhardness of samples in the solid solution region increases depending on the composition. The microhardness value for alloys containing the CrAsTe₃ compound increases from 850 MPa to 920 MPa. The microhardness of the

β-solid solution based on the CuCr₂Te₄ compound increased from 1850 MPa to 1880 MPa. The microhardness of two-phase region alloys remains unchanged depending on the composition.

Table 1.

Composition of alloys of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system, results of DTA, density and microhardness measurements

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/cm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
CrAsTe ₃	CuCr ₂ Te ₄			CrAsTe ₃	α
				P=0,10 N	P=0,15N
100	0.0	375	6,57	850	-
95	5,0	310,370,840	6,57	870	-
90	10	310, 360,825	6,56	920	-
80	20	310,800	6,56	920	-
70	30	310,525,720	6,56	920	-
60	40	310,515	6,55	-	1880
50	50	310,650,870	6,55	-	1880
40	60	310,650,970	6,55	-	1880
30	70	310,650,1045	6,54	-	1880
20	80	310,650,820,1100	6,53	-	1880
10	90	690,780,970,1075	6,52	-	1880
5,0	95	760,800,1145	6,52	-	1870
0,0	100	810,1155	6,51	-	1850

As a result of the research, a state diagram of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system was constructed (Fig. 3). As can be seen from Figure 3, the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system is a partially quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary As₂Te₃-CuTe-Cr₂Te₃ system. In the solid state, this system looks like a stable diagonal.

The liquidus of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system is limited by the monovariant equilibrium curves of Cr₂Te₃ and the β-solid solution based on the CuCr₂Te₄

compound. As a result of reprecipitation, a three-phase field of composition (L+CrAsTe₃+Cr₂Te₃) is formed in the range of 0-20 mol % CuCr₂Te₄. Above the solidus line in the range of 20-90 mol % CuCr₂Te₄ there is a three-phase region consisting of (L+Cr₂Te₃+α). In this case, a peritectic transformation occurs in the system and the compound L+Cr₂Te₃↔ CrAsTe₃ is formed, as a result of which phases consisting of (CrAsTe₃+α) crystallize below the solidus line.

Fig. 3. T-x phase diagram of the CrAsTe₃-CuCr₂Te₄ system.

Concludes

Alloys of the $\text{CrAsTe}_3\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system were studied using methods of physicochemical analysis and a T-x phase diagram was constructed. The phase diagram of the system is partially quasi-binary. Eutectic equilibrium and peritectic transformation occur in the system. In the $\text{CrAsTe}_3\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system based on the CuCr_2Te_4 compound, solid solutions are formed up to 8 mol % CrAsTe_3 , and solid solutions based on CrAsTe_3 are practically not established. The CrAsTe_3 compound decomposes according to the following reaction: $\text{CrAsTe}_3 \leftrightarrow \text{L} + \text{Cr}_2\text{Te}_3$. As a result of decay above the solidus line, three-phase regions appear, consisting of $(\text{L} + \text{Cr}_2\text{Te}_3 + \text{CrAsTe}_3)$ and $(\text{L} + \text{Cr}_2\text{Te}_3 + \alpha)$. Below the solidus line, two-phase alloys ($\text{CrAsTe}_3 + \alpha$) crystallize.

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